

PRIN 2022 RESIST

DELIVERABLE 6000-A

31-07-2025

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report outlines the development of a multi-scenario simulation framework to support defining redesign actions to be implemented on the experimental plant in order to enhance the overall resilience performance. Building on previous work (D5000-A) integrating the two different DTs, the current phase focuses on addressing key limitations of earlier models. The enhanced simulation environment enables a more realistic analysis of system behavior across a broad range of operational and stress scenarios. These simulations enable data-driven redesign actions aimed at improving system resilience, while maintaining compatibility with human-in-the-loop interactions. The report is structured to present the multi-scenario simulation improvements over prior stages, detailing the upgrades and the consequent results. Following the multi-scenario analysis, a list of redesign actions is presented to help improve the resilience factor of the case study system, but also for other general applications.

2. THE EXPERIMENTAL MULTI-SCENARIO SIMULATIONS

This chapter addresses the key limitations identified in the previous phase of the project and presents the solutions implemented to overcome them. Specific challenges related to time horizons, misalignment of key events and time series length are discussed in detail. By analyzing these constraints, it is possible to highlight the improvements introduced in the current multi-scenario simulation framework, which enable a more accurate and comprehensive representation of the experimental system's behavior.

2.1. Differing time horizons between normal and disrupted operation datasets

The primary challenge in the resilience computation lies in the differing lengths of the time series data between standard (normal) and disrupted operational scenarios. In many real-world applications, especially in cyber-physical systems or industrial control environments, data related to the duration of a disruption usually do not align with the operational timeline of the system. In other words, data collected during disruptions often span shorter or have irregular durations compared to the baseline operational data. This discrepancy leads to a fundamental issue: the resilience metric, which here relies on comparing the area under the performance curves of standard and disrupted scenarios, becomes skewed when the datasets are not of equal length, making it impossible to calculate it coherently. The resilience metric was here defined as:

$$R = \frac{A_s - |A_s - A_d|}{A_s}$$

where A_s and A_d represent the areas under the standard and disrupted performance curves, respectively. However, a simple trim of the longest curve to fit with the shorter one may not be enough. If the disrupted dataset is inadequately trimmed, it may exclude recovery phases or long-term effects, leading to an underestimation of the disruption's impact. Conversely, if the standard dataset is inadequately trimmed, it may inflate A_s , artificially boosting the resilience score even when the disruption is severe. To address this, the proposed methodology trims both datasets to the same length N , using the shortest of the two as a reference while ensuring that the disruption window is fully captured. This preprocessing step is crucial for ensuring that resilience is computed over a

comparable and meaningful time frame, ensuring a fair comparison and an accurate estimation. Figure 1 illustrates the issue discussed in this paragraph, with respect to data related to the water tank level sensor. Specifically, the standard curve (blue curve cf. Figure 1) is shorter than the disrupted curve (Red curve, cf. Figure 1), making it impossible to coherently compare the two with the resilience formula described above.

Figure 1. Standard vs disrupted curve plot.

2.2. Misalignment in the timing of key events across performance profiles management

Another critical issue in the resilience computation is the misalignment of events across standard and disrupted performance profiles. Even when the overall behavior of the system remains consistent, slight temporal shifts, such as delays in response, detection, or recovery, can cause significant discrepancies in point-by-point comparisons. This is particularly problematic in time series analysis, where resilience metrics often rely on synchronized data points. Without proper alignment, even similar performance patterns may appear drastically different, leading to misleadingly low resilience scores. This phenomenon is especially evident when using the absolute difference $|A_s - A_d|$ in the resilience formula, which becomes large if the curves are out of phase. To address this, the proposed methodology incorporates Dynamic Time Warping (DTW), a technique designed to align time series that may vary in speed or timing. DTW works by finding an optimal match between two sequences that minimizes the cumulative distance between their elements, allowing for non-linear alignments. Given two sequences:

$$X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N)$$

and

$$Y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N)$$

the DTW constructs a cost matrix D where each element $D(i, j)$ represents the distance between x_i and y_j using – in this case – the Euclidean distance:

$$D(i, j) = (x_i - y_j)^2$$

The goal is to find a warping path:

$$W = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_K)$$

where each $w_k = (i_k, j_k)$ aligns elements from X and Y , such that the total cost is minimized:

$$DTW(X, Y) = \min \sum_{k=1}^K D(i_k, j_k)$$

The DTW path must satisfy the boundary conditions (start and end at the first and last elements), the continuity of the timeseries (steps of size 1), and the monotonicity of the timeseries (preserve time order). The result is a flexible alignment that allows similar patterns to be compared even if they occur at different times.

By applying the DTW before computing resilience, the proposed method ensures that the performance deviations are assessed based on actual behavioral differences rather than timing mismatches, enhancing the robustness and the interpretability of the resilience metric. Figure 2 depicts the output of the DTW alignment step on the standard (orange curve, cf. Figure 2) and the disrupted (blue curve, cf. Figure 2) curves, showing how the two are perfectly aligned at the beginning and at the end, where no disruptions occur.

Figure 2. DTW application results.

2.3. Managing excessively long time series

Excessively long time series data presents a challenge for the resilience analysis, particularly when disruptions are short-lived relative to the overall dataset. In such cases, the area under the standard performance curve A_s becomes disproportionately large, which can lead to the resilience metric to be underestimated. In fact, as the considered resilience formulation normalizes the difference between the standard and the disrupted performance by A_s , a large denominator can mask the severity of significant disruptions, resulting in misleadingly high resilience scores. In the example of Figure 2, the beginning and the ending segments of the time series stress this problem making both the areas A_s and A_d unnecessarily big. To address this issue, the proposed method incorporates a targeted trimming strategy that isolates only the segments of the time series relevant to a disruption occurrence. This is achieved through an anomaly detection logic based on a user-defined threshold,

and two minimum duration criteria. The three parameters were empirically validated and set at 5% for the threshold, 50 timesteps for the minimum duration of an anomaly period, and 500 timesteps for the minimum duration of a non-anomaly period. In other words, whenever the script identifies a point with more than 5% difference between the two time series it starts counting how many others are subsequent. If the count reaches 50, the period is classified as anomaly, and it is not trimmed out. The anomalous periods end once 500 non-anomalous points in a row are spotted by the script. Once identified, non-anomalous segments are excluded from the calculation setting their value to 0, eventually ensuring that resilience is computed only over the period where the system's performance deviates from the norm. Via this approach, it is possible to enhance the sensitivity and the interpretability of the resilience metric, focusing the analysis on the most critical periods only. Figure 3 shows the same time series presented in Figure 2, but after the additional trimming of non-anomalous periods described above.

Figure 3. DTW trimming results.

3. MULTI-SCENARIO ANALYSIS

The analysis of experimental data from two cyber-attack scenarios targeting sensors S6 and S5 offered valuable insights into how novice and expert operators manage disruptions in an automated industrial system. It is here important to recall that the system under investigation is a mockup plant simulating natural gas extraction using water and air, where pressure and flow are controlled to maintain a stable two-phase mixture, thus the overall performance metrics of the plant can be seen as the amount of air drowned in (i.e., S7), and the amount of output water (both flow rate and volume generated).

In the first scenario, the attack compromises sensor S6, which monitors the water level inside the tank. Expert operators detect the failure significantly faster than novices, with an average detection time of 261.798 seconds compared to 433.982 seconds, i.e., a difference of nearly three minutes. This gap underscores the experts' superior situational awareness and familiarity with the plant's behavior. Moreover, the standard deviation in detection time is notably lower for experts (i.e., 56.155 seconds) than for novices (i.e., 105.556 seconds), indicating more consistent performance. Restoration times, however, are nearly identical between the two groups: 30.716 seconds for experts, and 30.612 seconds

for novices, both with a minimal variability, suggesting that the recovery procedures are standardized and equally accessible to both groups once the issue is identified.

Resilience metrics across the system reveal further distinctions. In the compromised sensor S6, experts show significantly higher resilience (0.818 vs. 0.706) and lower variability (standard deviation of 0.039 vs. 0.074), suggesting a more reliable ability to stabilize the system despite the loss of direct visibility. Experts likely compensate by relying on indirect indicators or inferred system states. For other sensors such as S1, S2, and S5, resilience values are similar, with novices slightly outperforming experts in S1 (0.883 vs. 0.877), though the difference is marginal and variability remains low. Both groups maintain high and nearly identical resilience in S5, indicating effective pressure management despite the attack on S6. Experts also show slightly better performance in S7 (0.755 vs. 0.732), with lower variability, reflecting more stable control over air intake.

Valve control metrics further highlight strategic differences. Experts demonstrate higher resilience if looking at AV1 behavior, the valve managing input water flow (0.334 vs. 0.281), with slightly lower variability, reinforcing their focus on stabilizing intake under uncertainty. They also outperform novices in AV2 and AV3, which control output water and air discharge. Although AV2 resilience is low overall, experts show a higher mean (0.084 vs. 0.049) and greater variability, suggesting a more assertive and potentially riskier approach. In AV3, experts again show slightly higher resilience (0.487 vs. 0.480) with lower variability, indicating steadier control.

Overall system output metrics reveal a trade-off. Experts maintain significantly higher resilience in output flow (0.436 vs. 0.306), with lower variability, indicating a stronger and more consistent focus on stabilizing this critical parameter. However, novices show higher resilience in total volume output (0.133 vs. 0.033), though with much greater variability. This suggests that while experts prioritize flow stability and rapid control, novices may adopt a more cautious approach, possibly due to uncertainty stemming from the compromised sensor.

In the second scenario, the cyber-attack targets sensor S5, which monitors pressure inside the tank, a central parameter for maintaining system stability and safety. Experts detect failures on average 50 seconds faster than novices, again demonstrating superior situational awareness. Restoration times remain similar, indicating consistent recovery protocols. Interestingly, experts exhibit slightly lower resilience in several key components (i.e., S1, S5, S6, and S7) all closely tied to pressure and fluid dynamics. This may reflect a more aggressive intervention strategy, where rapid control efforts introduce temporary instabilities that ripple through the system. Nonetheless, resilience in S5 remains the higher detected for both groups, with experts showing slightly lower variability, suggesting effective recovery despite the disruption. Resilience in S2, which measures input flow rate, is marginally higher for experts, indicating better regulation of incoming water. However, the input flowrate remains the most disrupted performance overall, highlighting the systemic impact of the attack on S5. Valve control metrics again show experts prioritizing input stability, with slightly higher resilience when looking at AV1. Conversely, they show slightly lower resilience if considering AV2 and AV3, suggesting a strategic compromise in tank stability to regain control over more critical parameters. This is consistent with their perception of persistent instability in the tank due to the disruption on S5.

As for the first scenario, experts also demonstrate slightly higher resilience in output flow, which was prioritized for stability. However, the total volume of water produced is marginally lower for experts, reflecting a conservative stance aimed at avoiding overproduction or system overload during instability. Overall, expert operators are shown faster and more decisive in responding to cyber

disruptions, often at the cost of temporary instability in certain aspects of plant performance. Their control strategies reflect a willingness to prioritize critical parameters such as pressure and flow, even if it means compromising others. Novice operators, while slower and more variable in their responses, tend to maintain slightly higher stability in some areas, likely due to more cautious or passive strategies.

This comparative analysis across both scenarios highlights the complex decision-making required in cyber-physical systems under attack, where speed and assertiveness must be balanced against caution and system-wide stability. The simulations showed how expert operators consistently demonstrate faster, more consistent, and strategically focused responses, while novices show a tendency toward conservative control, with greater variability but occasional advantages in output stability.

The resilience factor calculated in the following tables is based on the formula introduced in Section 2.1 (and previously presented in deliverable D5000-A). The detection time t_{det} is defined as the time difference between the moment the operator shuts down the system (t_{sd}) and the time when the attack begins (t_{att}),

$$t_{det} = t_{sd} - t_{att}$$

while the restoration time t_{rest} is computed as the time spent between the beginning of the operator's recovery actions (t_{rec}) and the moment at which the system regains full operative performance (t_{sup}),

$$t_{rest} = t_{sup} - t_{rec}$$

leading to a new start up. All the times are expressed in seconds.

Table 1 – Scenario 1, expert operator data.

<i>EXPERT (Scenario 1)</i>	<i>detection Time</i>	<i>restoratio nTime</i>	<i>resilien ceS1</i>	<i>resilien ceS2</i>	<i>resilien ceS5</i>	<i>resilien ceS6</i>	<i>resilien ceS7</i>	<i>resilienc eAV1</i>	<i>resilienc eAV2</i>	<i>resilienc eAV3</i>	<i>resilienceFl owOUT</i>	<i>resilienceVol umeOUT</i>
mean	261.798	30.716	0.877	0.375	0.881	0.818	0.755	0.334	0.084	0.487	0.436	0.033
std	56.155	1.654	0.015	0.007	0.001	0.039	0.013	0.051	0.048	0.021	0.041	0.026
min	143.000	28.000	0.776	0.369	0.873	0.675	0.720	0.232	0.000	0.429	0.295	0.000
25%	220.000	29.000	0.868	0.371	0.881	0.782	0.747	0.296	0.057	0.476	0.409	0.012
50%	254.000	30.000	0.878	0.373	0.881	0.824	0.754	0.334	0.087	0.486	0.444	0.026
75%	301.000	32.000	0.886	0.374	0.881	0.849	0.765	0.370	0.125	0.498	0.462	0.049
max	417.000	33.000	0.900	0.393	0.882	0.888	0.798	0.451	0.226	0.577	0.557	0.121

Table 2 – Scenario 1, novice operator data.

<i>NOVICE (Scenario 1)</i>	<i>detection Time</i>	<i>restoratio nTime</i>	<i>resilien ceS1</i>	<i>resilien ceS2</i>	<i>resilien ceS5</i>	<i>resilien ceS6</i>	<i>resilien ceS7</i>	<i>resilienc eAV1</i>	<i>resilienc eAV2</i>	<i>resilienc eAV3</i>	<i>resilienceFl owOUT</i>	<i>resilienceVol umeOUT</i>
mean	433.982	30.612	0.883	0.376	0.881	0.706	0.732	0.281	0.049	0.480	0.306	0.133
std	105.556	1.679	0.014	0.007	0.001	0.074	0.018	0.052	0.037	0.026	0.077	0.069
min	184.000	28.000	0.820	0.369	0.879	0.481	0.687	0.165	0.000	0.429	0.172	0.001
25%	358.500	29.000	0.870	0.371	0.880	0.670	0.720	0.242	0.017	0.463	0.237	0.083
50%	426.500	30.000	0.889	0.373	0.881	0.700	0.733	0.275	0.044	0.482	0.288	0.127
75%	509.000	32.000	0.893	0.377	0.881	0.768	0.747	0.318	0.071	0.494	0.376	0.181
max	709.000	33.000	0.900	0.393	0.882	0.878	0.774	0.446	0.190	0.524	0.501	0.313

Table 3– Scenario 2, expert operator data.

<i>EXPERT (Scenario 2)</i>	<i>detection Time</i>	<i>restoratio nTime</i>	<i>resilien ceS1</i>	<i>resilien ceS2</i>	<i>resilien ceS5</i>	<i>resilien ceS6</i>	<i>resilien ceS7</i>	<i>resilienc eAV1</i>	<i>resilienc eAV2</i>	<i>resilienc eAV3</i>	<i>resilienceFl owOUT</i>	<i>resilienceVol umeOUT</i>
mean	238.170	1590.710	0.246	0.059	0.803	0.768	0.523	0.241	0.212	0.342	0.560	0.427
std	18.253	118.542	0.065	0.003	0.001	0.015	0.043	0.056	0.024	0.036	0.028	0.012
min	193.000	1429.000	0.215	0.055	0.801	0.746	0.463	0.084	0.161	0.279	0.523	0.405
25%	225.750	1442.000	0.215	0.055	0.801	0.750	0.480	0.188	0.194	0.324	0.535	0.415
50%	240.000	1606.000	0.218	0.058	0.803	0.771	0.522	0.228	0.205	0.338	0.558	0.429
75%	252.000	1737.000	0.220	0.063	0.804	0.779	0.571	0.310	0.241	0.346	0.588	0.437
max	280.000	1739.000	0.405	0.064	0.805	0.793	0.618	0.335	0.252	0.460	0.661	0.448

Table 4 – Scenario 2, novice operator data.

<i>NOVICE (Scenario 2)</i>	<i>detection Time</i>	<i>restoratio nTime</i>	<i>resilien ceS1</i>	<i>resilien ceS2</i>	<i>resilien ceS5</i>	<i>resilien ceS6</i>	<i>resilien ceS7</i>	<i>resilienc eAV1</i>	<i>resilienc eAV2</i>	<i>resilienc eAV3</i>	<i>resilienceFl owOUT</i>	<i>resilienceVol umeOUT</i>
mean	288.622	1597.218	0.249	0.059	0.803	0.768	0.538	0.228	0.213	0.364	0.556	0.437
std	40.528	120.752	0.062	0.004	0.001	0.016	0.037	0.054	0.019	0.046	0.025	0.014
min	207.000	1429.000	0.213	0.053	0.801	0.742	0.463	0.084	0.161	0.285	0.488	0.408
25%	257.000	1442.000	0.216	0.055	0.802	0.752	0.506	0.181	0.199	0.330	0.541	0.426
50%	283.000	1606.000	0.219	0.058	0.803	0.770	0.551	0.219	0.213	0.347	0.553	0.438
75%	315.000	1737.000	0.223	0.063	0.804	0.778	0.569	0.277	0.228	0.390	0.575	0.447
max	392.000	1739.000	0.457	0.064	0.808	0.799	0.628	0.332	0.259	0.462	0.670	0.468

3.1. Overall resilience performance metrics

This paragraph outlines an evaluation of the plant’s resilience using two key metrics that reflect its overall performance. Since the mockup simulates oil extraction from a depleted well, the analysis focuses on the following parameters:

- Flow OUT, which relates to the system’s ability to sustain a consistent water (thus, oil) throughput;
- S7 (i.e., air inlet flowrate), which relates to the system’s capacity to maintain vacuum/suction efficiency at the ejector inlet, eventually ensuring a stable pressure support for the reservoir.

Figure 4, Figure 6, Figure 6, and Figure 7 include four scatterplots related to the aforementioned metrics for Scenario 1 related to a cyber-attack targeting the water level sensor. Please note that the resilience values are plotted against the detection time only because the analysis of results presented in Section 3 shows how the variations in restoration time are minimal and less impactful on resilience.

Both the plots clearly demonstrate that a rapid anomaly recognition is the strongest determinant of system resilience. However, the novices’ performance reveals a surprising rebound effect at very long detection delays. In the water flow plot in Figure 4, expert operators (orange points) cluster tightly within a 150 - 300 seconds detection window, with resilience values ranging from approximately 0.40 to 0.60. This indicates both prompt identification and a quite stable way of controlling the water output despite the detection, even if a relatively consistent loss on performance. In contrast, novices (blue points, cf. Figure 6) display a broader distribution with most detection times comprised between 350 and 700 seconds, and definitely low resilience values ranging from 0.15 to 0.45, confirming that delayed detection significantly compromises the recovery performance. Interestingly, at detection times beyond 600 seconds, several novice data points exhibit a rebound in resilience scores, reaching levels comparable to those seen with much earlier detections. This apparent recovery is not necessarily indicative of an improved operator performance but is nonetheless a compelling and noteworthy result. One possible explanation is that some novices adopt a passive “let-it-run” strategy when confronted with ambiguous signals or minor anomalies, delaying corrective valve actions out of caution. During this period of inaction, being the cyber-attack on the level sensor, the plant’s PID controllers continue to regulate pressures and flows, keeping the system relatively stable until intervention finally occurs. However, a more intriguing interpretation is that the least experienced or “weaker” novices (i.e., those who perform poorly in general) may actually benefit from a less constrained and more improvisational response style. While being forced to adapt without relying on refined routines or prior expectations, they might stand on more flexible or exploratory strategies that momentarily enhance performance, even under stress. From this perspective, extensive experience – while typically advantageous – could also foster more rigid, less adaptive behaviors. This is perhaps reflected in the experts’ resilience plots, which tend to be more uniform and less exploratory in nature.

The air-intake scatterplot in Figure 6 and Figure 7 reinforces the broader conclusions, but with a less evident rebound distortion. Experts form a compact, best-performing cluster between 150 - 400 seconds detection times, and resilience scores around 0.75 - 0.80, reflecting a good management of suction performance. Novices, by contrast, show a greater resilience decline as detection delays increase, dropping down to 0.70 or lower for detection times beyond 500 seconds.

Figure 4. Flow out resilience performance comparison, Scenario 1, detailed on expert.

Figure 5. Flow out resilience performance comparison, Scenario 1, detailed on novice.

Figure 6. S7 resilience comparison, Scenario 1, detailed on expert.

Figure 7. S7 resilience comparison, Scenario 1, detailed on novice.

Similarly, Figure 8, Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11 plot the detection time against the resilience computed by means of the water flowrate and the air intake, respectively, for Scenario 2, in which the tank-pressure sensor S5 is compromised. As for Scenario 1, restoration times show minimal variations, so the analysis focuses exclusively on detection time.

In both plots, expert operators (orange points, cf. Figure 8 and Figure 10) remain tightly clustered within the 200 - 350 seconds detection window, achieving not really high but yet quite consistent resilience values: ranging approximately between 0.45 - 0.60 for air flowrate, and between 0.50 - 0.60 for water output flowrate. Novice operators (blue points, cf. Figure 9 and Figure 11) follow a similar pattern. However, with respect to water output flowrate resilience, at around 350 second, the novice performance curiously degrades on average stabilizing around the lower bound of 0.5.

This threshold-driven dropdown reveals two key characteristics of Scenario 2's pressure-sensitive dynamics. First, early detection remains crucial, and once a sensor breach goes unrecognized beyond a certain point, pressure oscillations intensify and rapidly challenges both manual adjustments and PID stabilization leading to a kind of “non-returning” point. Second, novices, who in Scenario 1, occasionally may have benefited from a passive “let-it-run” approach, now find that strategy counterproductive: in a pressure-based disruption, simulations show how delaying actions cause the system to move away from its target values more quickly and permanently, making it harder to maintain high resilience performance.

Figure 8. Flow out resilience performance comparison in Scenario 2, detail on expert.

Figure 9. Flow out resilience performance comparison in Scenario 2, detail on novice.

Figure 10. S7 resilience comparison, Scenario 2, detail on expert.

Figure 11. S7 resilience comparison, Scenario 2, detail on novice.

The findings presented in this section highlight that early detection is the most important factor for maintaining system resilience during cyber-physical attacks. Expert operators generally perform better, showing more stable and reliable control strategies, especially when problems are detected quickly. Interestingly, simulations showed how some novice operators manage to show higher resilience at longer detection times, likely by relying on more flexible or improvised actions. This seems to help particularly in Scenario 1, where the system stays relatively stable for a while on its own. But in Scenario 2, where pressure changes cause instability, that kind of passive or delayed response becomes much less effective. Overall results highlight that while experience leads to more consistent results, it might also lead to more rigid behavior. On the other hand, operators sometimes benefit from being more open or adaptable, but it may not be enough, especially in particular situations (as the one in Scenario 2). The contrast raises interesting questions about the trade-offs between controllability and adaptability, especially in such dynamic and complex operational contexts. Indeed, building resilience in complex systems likely requires a mixture of strong expertise and the ability to adapt when things do not go as expected. However, such benefits are highly scenario-dependent and unreliable under (e.g.) pressure-sensitive failures, suggesting the need for both robust automation support capable of helping lower detection times, and a comprehensive operator training meant at balancing experience with adaptive thinking.

4. REDESIGN ACTIONS

Based on the insights gained through the multi-scenario simulations, this chapter outlines a set of redesign actions aimed at enhancing system resilience. These actions, which are listed in Table 5, are derived from data-driven evaluations and are intended to address specific vulnerabilities identified during the simulation phase. Table 6, instead, presents general redesign actions, which are independent from the simulated data.

The tables are organized along two criteria: the level of implementation effort and the type of actor involved in the redesign. The effort levels (medium-low and medium-high) are determined based on a combined evaluation of cost, required time, and impact on the system, as estimated within the specific context of the analyzed plant. These values are therefore localized and reflect the characteristics and constraints of this particular system. It is important to note that the same redesign action may require different levels of effort when applied to other plants or operational contexts. The actors are classified into three categories: the technical system (plant-level interventions), the human operator, and the entire organization, meaning actions that involve both technological and human components.

Each cell in the tables represents a unique combination of effort level and actor, and includes the corresponding redesign actions. These actions are labeled using a three-letter code, where the first two letters indicate the effort level (i.e., ML for Medium-Low), and the second letter refers to the actor involved (i.e., H for Human). This structure is intended to facilitate a quick overview and categorization of the actions, helping prioritize interventions based on their feasibility and scope. Cells marked with a “-” indicate that no relevant insights emerged for the corresponding combination.

Table 5. Data-driven redesign actions.

		<i>Plant</i>	<i>Human</i>	<i>Organizational (plant and human)</i>
<i>Cost + Impact + Time</i>	Medium-Low	ML_P1: Sensor redundancy ML_P2: Valve control strategy optimization	-	ML_O1: Novice operators interface support
	Medium-High	MH_P1: Functional segmentation for anomaly containment	MH_H1: Training for resilience and adaptability	-

- *ML_P1 - Sensor Redundancy*: the results indicate that the failure or compromise of a single sensor (i.e., S5 or S6) can significantly affect the entire system. It may therefore be useful to incorporate redundant sensors or systems capable of indirectly estimating critical parameters, such as inferring water level from flow rates and the static characteristics of the system’s components. Implementing data fusion techniques could further enhance the system’s robustness in scenarios where data is missing or corrupted;
- *ML_P2 - Valve control strategy optimization*: the data suggest that expert operators tend to prioritize the stability of the inlet valve (AV1), sometimes at the expense of the outlet valves (AV2, AV3). It may be beneficial to redesign the valve control logic to achieve a better balance between inlet and outlet flows. For instance, implementing an algorithm that optimizes the operation of all valves proportionally could help maintain overall system alignment;
- *ML_O1 - Novice Operators Interface Support*: the findings show that experienced operators are better able to compensate for missing data, likely due to their expertise, despite all operators having access to the same interface information. Enhancing the interface by integrating indicators that reflect the “decision-making process” of expert operators could assist less experienced users in making more effective decisions;

- *MH_P1 - Functional segmentation for anomaly containment*: in the analyzed plant, it was observed that the malfunction of a single sensor (i.e., S6) can affect the entire process. This vulnerability could be mitigated by implementing detection and control architectures able to segment the plant into distinct, functionally independent modules. In this way, potential anomalies could remain confined within specific subsystems preventing from propagating across the entire process. While this approach can be useful even in smaller systems, its benefits become especially relevant as system complexity and size increase, making it a key design strategy for enhancing resilience in large-scale industrial settings;
- *MH_H1 - Training for resilience and adaptability*: less experienced operators exhibit greater variability and longer response times. Training programs focused on managing attack scenarios should be considered as a means to reduce response variability. However, such training should also take into account the interesting observation that very inexperienced operators, despite longer response times, may still exhibit increased resilience. This suggests the need to strike a balance between providing structured guidelines (controllability) and preserving flexibility in decision-making (adaptability);

Table 6. General redesign actions.

		<i>Plant</i>	<i>Human</i>	<i>Organizational (plant and human)</i>
Cost + Impact + Time	Medium- Low	-	ML_H1: Patterns redesign ML_H2: Mocap equipment alternatives	ML_O2: AI integration
	Medium- High	MH_P2: Parallel DT for system security	-	MH_O1: Crisis management protocols

- *ML_H1 - Patterns redesign*: one of the fastest ways to improve the response time from the operator is to redesign the patterns to follow during the inspections, streamlining (where possible) the process and minimizing unnecessary steps. It could also be possible to equip the operator with mixed reality tools to support them during the routine;
- *ML_H2 - Mocap equipment alternatives*: it could be possible to use other technologies instead of inertial Mocap systems (as used in the RESIST project) to obtain operators' data. The choice can be made considering plant constraints (i.e., lots of metallic material that can create an electromagnetic field, altering inertial Mocap recording accuracy), equipment costs, privacy matters and other specific reasons;
- *ML_O2 - AI integration*: The integration of AI within the plant, used for performance analysis, system management, and decision support could enhance crisis management. AI enables real-time monitoring to help early anomaly detection, reducing risks and preventing failures. During crises, it can automatically adjust operations and guide operators in making informed, timely decisions by synthesizing complex data. This could reduce cognitive overload, accelerate response times and minimize human error, ultimately improving resilience by enabling quicker, more effective responses to critical situations;

- *MH_P2 - Parallel DT for system security*: implementing a Parallel Digital Twin (PDT), physically isolated from networks but connected to plant sensors and valves, to enhance resilience against cyber threats. Operating in passive mode, it replicates predictive models and control logic to detect anomalies and, if needed, disconnect the remote DT and take control. This solution offers a proactive safety layer with moderate costs, leveraging existing models and infrastructure. Future integration with a human DT would enable plant-operator co-simulation in critical scenarios;
- *MH_O1 - Crisis management protocols*: developing a protocol that guides the operator, regardless of the seniority, could wrap up all the informations needed to better face a crisis. The informations could be the ones listed on the dashboard, the training and others considered useful and derived from previous experiences or simulations.

Each redesign action contributes to the enhancement of resilience by addressing different aspects of the system. However, no single intervention can be deemed universally more critical than others, nor should it be prioritized over them in all cases. The importance and sequence of implementation depend on the plant's specific needs and context, including factors such as existing vulnerabilities, operational goals, and external constraints. Therefore, the selection and prioritization of redesign actions should be tailored to the unique requirements of the plant, ensuring a balanced approach that improves resilience holistically.

5. CONCLUSION

This report builds on the previous WP5000 work on critical scenario simulations conducted across two distinct operative scenarios, and addresses the limitations identified in the earlier research stage. The enhanced multi-scenario simulations overcome the limits of differing time horizons between normal and disrupted operation datasets, misalignment in the timing of key events and managing excessively long time series, providing more realistic and reliable data.

The findings emphasize that early detection is critical for maintaining system resilience during cyber-physical attacks. Expert operators typically perform better, demonstrating stable and reliable control, especially when problems are detected quickly. Interestingly, novice operators sometimes show higher resilience with longer detection times, likely due to more flexible or improvised actions. This was particularly noticeable in Scenario 1, where the system remained stable despite delayed responses. However, in Scenario 2, where pressure changes induced instability, delayed reactions proved less effective. These results underscore the trade-off between control and adaptability, suggesting that resilience in complex systems requires a balance between experience and flexibility. This balance, however, is highly scenario-dependent, highlighting the need for both automation, to reduce detection times, and comprehensive operator training to promote a mix of expertise and adaptability.

Based on the simulation data, several redesign actions were identified to improve the resilience of the system. These include functional segmentation for anomaly containment and operator training to improve both adaptability and resilience. Additionally, improvements in sensors redundancy and enhancing the operator's user interface were proposed to strengthen the overall system resilience.

Beyond the plant-specific context, other general redesign actions were listed, including the implementation of AI modules to accelerate human and plant response time or developing crisis management modules to standardize response protocols.

Although these actions vary in priority, depending on the plant's immediate needs (i.e., system stability vs operator training), and in impact (considering factors like technological complexity or cost), they collectively enhance the plant's ability to effectively respond to disruptions, ensuring better resilience performances. In conclusion, these redesign actions offer a comprehensive approach to strengthening both the technical and human aspects of the system, ultimately ensuring a more resilient and adaptive plant capable of withstanding cyber-physical challenges.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) – Mission 4 Education and Research – Component 2 From research to business - Investment 1.1, Prin 2022 Notice announced with DD No. 104 of 2/2/2022, entitled RESIST - RESilience management to Industrial Systems Threats, proposal code 2022YSAE2X